

First record of *Leucauge argyrescens* Benoit, 1978 from South Africa (Araneae: Tetragnathidae)

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ABSTRACT: We present the first records of the black-spot silver marsh spider *Leucauge argyrescens* Benoit, 1978 from South Africa. This African endemic species was previously known only from the Comoros and Seychelles. The general morphology is discussed and photographs are provided, with notes on their behaviour, distribution, and conservation status.

Key words: biodiversity, distribution, new record, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA)

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Leucauge* White, 1841 is known from 182 species and sub-species with 36 known from Africa (World Spider Catalog, 2022). As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), large areas in South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) were sampled, and many members of the family Tetragnathidae were collected.

Several specimens of a small *Leucauge* species were identified as *Leucauge argyrescens* Benoit, 1978, a species previously known only from the Comoros and Seychelles. The species is possibly under-sampled and expected to occur in more African countries, but is reported here from South Africa for the first time. We present photographs of live specimens to demonstrate the general morphology and colouration, and notes are provided on their behaviour, distribution, and conservation status in the country.

METHODS

Several photographs were sent to the SANSA Virtual Museum database (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012) as shown here. Voucher specimens of the specimens collected during surveys are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria.

TAXONOMY

Leucauge argyrescens Benoit, 1978

Leucauge argyrescens Benoit, 1978: 671; Locket, 1980: 122; Saaristo, 2003: 17; 2010: 230.

Leucauge russellsmithi Locket, 1980: 122 (syn).

MORPHOLOGY

Diagnostic characteristics: Size: TL female 3.5 mm, male 2.05 mm. *Leucauge argyrescens* is a small species that can be distinguished by the more or less globose abdomen (Figs 1 & 2). Female: carapace uniform fawn with an irregular median band; sternum whitish-yellow, with long setae. Abdomen fawn with blackish posterior end with three pairs of small yellow to silvery spots (Figs 3 & 4); the spots' colour varies, as in some specimens it was red (Figs 11–13). Legs: coxae and femora coloured as carapace; tibiae, metatarsi, and tarsi darkened. Epigyne with atrium square shaped (Fig. 7). Male: carapace pale yellow; sternum same colour as carapace, but with dusky radiations and thin black borderline. Abdomen darkened posteriorly; light silver patches dorsolaterally and ventrally (Fig. 10). Femora colour similar to carapace; tibiae I and II darkening gradually to the apex; metatarsi similar, with some darkening also on III and IV. Palp recognised by the relatively large, pointed conductor, slightly notched paracymbium, and unmodified cymbium (Fig. 8).

Figures 1–2. *Leucauge argyrescens*: 1. Female dorsal view. 2. Female lateral view, both from Wakefield Farm near Hillcrest. Photo credits: Peter Webb.

Figures 3–9: *Leucauge argyrescens*: 3. Female lateral view. 4. Female dorsal view from Mazeppa Bay. 5. Female dorsal view. 6. Abdomen ventrum. 7. Epigyne. 8. Male palp. 9. Epigyne female from Mazeppa Bay. Photo credits: 3, 4, 9 Charles Haddad. 5–8 Line drawings after Locket (1980).

BEHAVIOUR

Small spider species that reside in orb-webs they build on low bushes and plants near the ground level. Species was sampled sweeping vegetation from the Forest, Savanna and Thicket Biomes in South Africa.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

The species has also been recorded from the Comoros, Seychelles, and is newly recorded from South Africa. It is under-sampled and expected to occur in more African countries.

DISTRIBUTION SOUTH AFRICA

Eastern Cape: East London Pineapple Research Station (-33.01, 27.90); Jeffreys Bay (-34.04, 24.94); Mazeppa Bay (-32.47, 28.64); Thyspunt (-34.206, 24.708); Storms River (-33.98, 23.83). **Gauteng:** Irene (field opposite Gem Village) (-25.89, 28.23); Pretoria National Botanical Garden (-25.74, 28.19). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); Wakefield Farm near Hillcrest (-29.5, 29.90). **Limpopo:** Entabeni State Forest (-23.00, 30.23); Swartbos Forest (-23.53, 29.59); Londolozi Game Reserve (-24.86, 31.53); Hanglip Forest (-23.04, 29.91).

Figures 10–13. *Leucauge argyrescens*: 10. Male from Jeffreys Bay. 11–12. Immature females from Thyspunt. 13. Juvenile from Storms River. Photo credits: 10–13. Linda Wiese.

Known distribution in South Africa

CONSERVATION

The species has a wide distribution in the Afrotropical Region but it is under-sampled in South Africa. It can be considered Least Concern.

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